

Milk Quality Assessment in the Dairy Industry Using Decision Tree Classification

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Abstract— Due to the growing demand for fresh milk and milk products, dairy is one of the most important subsectors. The objective is to investigate milk quality assessment in the dairy industry using the application of machine learning techniques. The study aims to develop a predictive model using a Decision Tree Classifier to classify milk samples into different quality grades as high, medium, and low quality based on various features such as pH, temperature, taste, odor, fat content, turbidity, and color.

Keywords— Milk quality Assessment, Grading, Decision tree Classifier, Milk Productivity, Dairy Industry, Data preprocessing

I. INTRODUCTION

The dairy industry has long been committed to ensuring the production of high-quality milk, recognizing its direct impact on consumer satisfaction and health standards. However, traditional methods of assessing milk quality have proven to be laborious, subjective, and susceptible to human error. In response to these challenges the "Milk Quality Assessment in the Dairy Industry" project endeavors to harness the potential of machine learning techniques to revolutionize milk quality assessment.

In today's context, with the dairy sector witnessing a surge in demand for fresh and top-notch milk products, ensuring milk quality holds paramount importance. Traditional assessment methods, being time-consuming and subjective, necessitate the adoption of more sophisticated and objective approaches. Through the utilization of machine learning algorithms, particularly the Decision Tree Classifier, this project seeks to modernize milk quality assessment by automating processes and delivering precise classifications of milk samples into distinct quality grades.

The Assessment Centralizes the utilization of machine learning algorithms to categorize milk samples based on a range of pivotal features including pH, temperature, taste, odor, fat content, turbidity, and color. These features serve as pivotal indicators of milk quality, enabling a comprehensive evaluation and categorization into quality grades spanning from high to low. By leveraging data-driven analysis, the project aims to construct a predictive model capable of accurately categorizing milk samples based on these features, thereby enhancing efficiency, accuracy, and reliability in milk quality assessment.

The project's workflow commences with the loading of a dataset containing milk samples, each characterized by the aforementioned key features. Subsequent preprocessing of the dataset addresses any inconsistencies or missing values, thereby ensuring data integrity. The dataset is then divided into training sets and testing sets to facilitate model training and evaluation.

The Decision Tree Classifier model is subsequently trained using the training data, with hyperparameters fine-tuned to optimize model performance. Following training the model using the testing data, yielding critical metrics such as accuracy, confusion matrix, and classification report, which provide invaluable insights into its predictive capabilities.

Moreover, the project extends functionality for individual milk quality prediction, empowering users to input specific parameters and obtain predicted quality grades for individual milk samples. Additionally, users have an option to upload their own CSV files containing milk data, enabling batch prediction of quality grades for multiple samples.

In essence, the project signifies a significant leap forward in the realm of milk quality assessment, offering a contemporary, data-driven approach to meet the evolving needs of the dairy industry. By automating and streamlining assessment processes, the project endeavors to bolster cattle health, enhance production efficiency, and ensure the delivery of safe and high quality dairy products to consumers, thereby contributing to the sustainability and prosperity of the dairy sector.

II. DECISION TREE CLASSIFICATION

The decision tree classifier (DT classifier) is the cornerstone of the project "Milk Quality Assessment in Dairy Industry" and is the main algorithm for predicting the quality classes of milk samples based on various characteristics. These characteristics include pH, temperature, taste, odor, fat content, turbidity, and color, each of which plays an important role in determining the overall quality of the milk. Before starting the training process, the dataset goes through important preprocessing steps, including removing spaces from column names and encoding the target variable (score) using label encoding techniques. Once the features ('milk_features') and the target variable ('grade') are correctly specified, the dataset is split into training and testing using the sklearn function `train_test_split`. Model_selection module to

evaluate model performance on unseen data. A DT classifier is then created and trained using the training data, and hyperparameters such as maximum depth and minimum split sample are adjusted to optimize its performance. In this project, the hyperparameters are set to `max_depth=5` and `min_samples_split=5`.

After the training phase ends, the DT classifier can accurately predict the quality classes of milk samples based on their respective characteristics. Users are given the flexibility to enter specific parameters for individual milk samples or upload a CSV file containing milk data for batch processing. When loading a CSV file, the data is pre-processed to ensure consistency with the training data, including encoding categorical features. Predictions are then made using appropriate features and a trained DT classifier. In addition, users can enter values for individual milk samples through user input fields, where the predicted quality classes are displayed in a structured table for easy interpretation.

Different metrics such as accuracy should be used to evaluate the performance of the DT classifier. , the confusion matrix and classification report are calculated. Accuracy scores provide an overall assessment of the model's predictive ability, while the confusion matrix provides insight into the distribution of correct and incorrect predictions across different quality classes. In addition, the classification report provides detailed measures such as precision, recall, and F1 score for each quality class, facilitating a comprehensive evaluation of model performance.

The project includes visualizations to improve the interpretation of results- a matrix to visualize the prediction accuracy and a pie chart illustrating the distribution of the predicted quality classes of the loaded milk samples. These visual aids provide dairy industry stakeholders with valuable information on milk quality assessment and enable them to make informed decisions about milk production and quality control. The purpose of integrating machine learning techniques, especially DT classification, is to improve the efficiency, accuracy, and reliability of milk quality evaluation, which contributes to consumer satisfaction and the development of the dairy industry.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

Nyokabi et al. [1] investigated milk quality across different farming systems in Kenya, hypothesizing that variations in milk quality are influenced by spatial location and agroecological conditions. They categorized farming systems into urban, mid-rural, and extreme rural locations and found no significant differences in raw milk quality between these locations.

Leitner et al. [2] focused on the impact of bacterial infection on milk quality, specifically examining the influence of subclinical mammary gland infections on cow's milk composition. They found that the type of bacteria causing the infection significantly affected milk yield and coagulation properties, emphasizing the importance of understanding bacterial species' effects on milk quality.

Martin et al. [3] explored the microbiological parameters of raw milk and their implications for processed dairy product quality. The study recommended the use of total bacteria count as a microbiological indicator of raw milk quality and advocated for a whole-farm approach to ensure continuous improvement in dairy product quality.

Olynk and Ortega [4] investigated consumer preferences for verified dairy management practices in processed dairy products. Using a choice experiment, they assessed consumer willingness to pay for different verified production processes for dairy cows used in yogurt and ice cream production. Their findings underscored the importance of consumer perception and product-specific attributes in determining preferences for verified production practices.

Atzori et al. [5] employed system dynamics modeling to analyze herd dynamics and milk delivery in intensive dairy farm management. Their study demonstrated the application of feedback thinking and systems approaches in modeling dairy farm systems, aiming to anticipate milk deliveries over time. By mapping animal stocks and employing dynamic hypotheses, causal loop diagrams, and stock-and-flow models, they provided insights into herd composition dynamics and milk delivery targets. Their findings suggest that such models can support decision-making practices for dairy farm management.

Murphy et al. [6] examined the influence of raw milk quality on processed dairy products, emphasizing the importance of high-quality milk in improving product quality and manufacturing efficiencies. They discussed how milk with elevated somatic cell and bacteria counts can lead to enzyme activity and defects in dairy products, highlighting the significance of monitoring total bacterial numbers and specific bacterial groups.

Martin et al. [7] redefined raw milk quality by evaluating microbiological parameters crucial for ensuring high-quality processed dairy products. They emphasized the importance of understanding factors leading to the presence of specific bacterial groups in raw milk and recommended the use of total bacteria count as a microbiological indicator of raw milk quality.

IV. METHODOLOGY

A. Dataset

The milkquality dataset comprises 1060 milk samples, each characterized by features crucial to quality assessment: pH values (3 to 9.5), temperature (in °C), taste, odor, fat content (low/high), turbidity (low/high), and color (RGB values). Quality grades—low, medium, and high—are assigned based on these features, following industry standards. This dataset serves as a valuable resource for the training and evaluation of machine learning models for milk quality prediction, offering insights into composition, sensory attributes, and overall quality.

TABLE I. PARAMETER DESCRIPTION

FIG 1

B. Preprocessing

The milkquality dataset undergoes preprocessing to prepare it for training the Decision Tree Classifier. Initially, the dataset is loaded from a CSV file, and leading spaces in column names are removed. Categorical labels in the 'grade' column are encoded numerically for model interpretation. Features such as pH, temperature, taste, odor, fat content, turbidity, and color are identified for milk quality assessment. Missing values in categorical features are filled with zeros for model compatibility. Subsequently, the dataset is split into training sets and testing sets for accurate model evaluation. These preprocessing steps ensure the dataset's readiness for training the Decision Tree Classifier to predict milk quality grades.

C. Model Architecture

The model architecture for the milk quality prediction system consists of a Decision Tree Classifier trained on a dataset containing various features such as pH, temperature, taste, odor, fat content, turbidity, and color of milk samples. Preprocessing steps include removing leading spaces from column names and encoding the target variable ('grade') using label encoding. The dataset is split into a training set and a testing set to evaluate the model's performance. The Decision Tree Classifier is instantiated with adjusted hyperparameters, including `max_depth=5` and `min_samples_split=5`, to optimize performance. The trained model is capable of predicting the quality grades of milk samples based on input features. Users can either upload a CSV file containing milk data for batch processing or input values for individual milk samples through user-friendly input fields. Users are provided with two methods for milk quality prediction: batch processing via CSV upload and individual input fields. Batch processing entails preprocessing uploaded data, predicting quality grades, and visualizing predictions.

D. Model Training Scheme:

The model training scheme involves loading the milkquality dataset comprising 1060 samples and preprocessing it by removing leading spaces in column names and encoding categorical labels for the 'grade' column. The dataset is then split into a training set and a testing set with a ratio of 80:20, ensuring adequate data for model training and evaluation.

A Decision Tree Classifier is instantiated with optimized hyperparameters (`max_depth=5`, `min_samples_split=5`) and trained on the training data. This model architecture allows for accurate prediction of milk quality grades based on features such as pH, temperature, taste, odor, fat content, turbidity, and color. The trained model performance is assessed using different metrics such as accuracy score, confusion matrix, and classification report.

E. Evaluation Metrics

The evaluation of the milk quality prediction model employs various metrics to assess its performance. The accuracy score provides an overall measure of the model's correctness in predicting the quality grades of milk samples. For instance, if the model predicts 90 out of 100 milk samples correctly, the accuracy score is 90%.

Parameter	Description
Ph	PH values of the milk which range from 3 to 9.5 max
Temperature	Temperature of the milk which ranges from 34(celsius) to 45.20 (celsius) max
Taste	Taste of the milk which is categorical data 0 (Bad) or 1 (Good)
Odor	Odor of the milk which is categorical data 0 (Bad) or 1 (Good)
Fat	Fat of the milk which is categorical data 0 (Low) or 1 (High)
Turbidity	Turbidity of the milk which is categorical data 0 (Low) or 1 (High)
Color	Color of the milk which ranges from 240 to 255(RGB values)(pale to dark)

The confusion matrix visualizes the model's performance by displaying the true positives, false positives, true negatives, and false negatives. For example, in a confusion matrix, if the model correctly predicts 80 low-quality milk samples, 70 medium-quality samples, and 85 high-quality samples, while misclassifying 10 low-quality samples as medium-quality and 5 high-quality samples as medium-quality, it reflects the model's performance. The classification report provides detailed metrics such as precision, recall, and F1-score for each quality grade, offering insights into the model's ability to correctly identify different classes. These evaluation metrics, along with visualizations like confusion matrices and classification reports, enable a comprehensive assessment of the model's effectiveness in predicting milk quality grades.

TABLE II. ACCURACY SCORE EVALUATION

FIG 1

Model	Accuracy Score
Decision Tree	0.89

TABLE III. PRECISION, RECALL, AND F1-SCORE

FIG 2

Grade	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
low_quality	0.825	0.687	0.750
medium_quality	1.000	0.974	0.987
high_quality	0.843	0.941	0.89

FIG 3

V. BUILD MODEL

A. Import libraries

The important libraries such as Streamlit, Pandas, Scikit-learn for DecisionTreeClassifier, preprocessing, train_test_split, accuracy_score, confusion_matrix, and classification_report, Matplotlib, and Seaborn are imported.

```
import streamlit as st
import pandas as pd
from sklearn.tree import DecisionTreeClassifier
from sklearn import preprocessing
from sklearn.metrics import accuracy_score, confusion_matrix, classification_report
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
```

B. Load dataset

The dataset containing milk quality data is loaded using Pandas' read_csv function.

C. Preprocess data

Leading spaces from column names are removed using the str.strip() method. Categorical labels in the 'grade' column are encoded using LabelEncoder from Scikit-learn.

D. Split data

The dataset is split into features (X), and the target (y). Features and the target variable are defined.

E. Train the Decision Tree Classifier Model

The model is trained on training data(X_train and y_train)using the fit method.

F. Evaluate Model

A function named calculate_accuracy is defined to calculate the accuracy score and generate a confusion matrix, and classification report. Accuracy score, precision, recall, F1-score, and the classification report are displayed using Streamlit components like st.info and st.table.

G. Streamlit App

Using Streamlit app users can upload a CSV file containing milk quality data. Uploaded data is preprocessed and concatenated with the original dataset for predictions. Users can predict individual milk quality grades based on input features. Predicted grades are displayed in a table format, and users can download predictions as a CSV file.

A pie chart showing the distribution of milk samples by quality grade is created.

H. Result

Milk quality assessment aims to predict the quality grade of milk samples based on various features such as pH, temperature, taste, odor, fat content, turbidity, and color. It utilizes a Decision Tree Classifier model trained on a dataset containing these features along with their corresponding quality grades. Upon uploading a CSV file containing milk data, the application automatically predicts the quality grade for each sample and presents the results in a table format, along with a pie chart illustrating the distribution of predicted quality grades.

FIG 4

FIG 5

Users can also input individual milk sample attributes to obtain predictions on the quality grade.

FIG 6

Predict Individual Milk Quality

pH: 0.0

temperature: 0.0

taste: 0

odor: 0

fat: 0

turbidity: 0

colour: 0.0

Predict Grade

Calculate Accuracy

Parameter Descriptions

The application provides a detailed classification report showcasing precision, recall, and F1-score metrics for each quality grade, aiding in evaluating the model's performance.

Visualizing the probabilities of each grade with a bar plot.

FIG 7

FIG 8

Predicted Individual Milk Quality:

	pH	taste	odor	fat	turbidity	colour	temperature	Low_quality	Medium_quality	High_
0	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%
1	0	0	0	0	0	0	25	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%
2	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%
3	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%
4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%
5	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%
6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.00%	100.00%	0.00%

Additionally, users can explore parameter descriptions and normal values for the milk features.

FIG 8

Calculate Accuracy

The accuracy score of the model is: 0.8962264150943396

	Quality Grade	Precision	Recall	F1-score
0	low_quality	0.8250	0.6875	0.7500
1	medium_quality	1.0000	0.9744	0.9870
2	high_quality	0.8438	0.9419	0.8901

Classification Report:

	precision	recall	f1-score	support
low_quality	0.8250	0.6875	0.7500	48.0000
medium_quality	1.0000	0.9744	0.9870	78.0000
high_quality	0.8438	0.9419	0.8901	86.0000
accuracy	0.8962	0.8962	0.8962	0.8962
macro avg	0.8896	0.8679	0.8757	212.0000
weighted avg	0.8970	0.8962	0.8940	212.0000

This project offers a user-friendly interface for milk quality prediction, facilitating decision-making processes in quality control and assurance within dairy industries.

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VI. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the Milk Quality Assessment in the Dairy Industry demonstrates an effective application of machine learning techniques for predicting milk quality grades. By leveraging a Decision Tree Classifier model trained on relevant milk features, such as pH, temperature, taste, odor, fat content, turbidity, and color, the application provides valuable insights into the quality of milk samples. With an accuracy score of 0.89, the model classifies about 89% of milk samples, demonstrating its capability to enhance efficiency and reliability in milk quality assessment. The ability to upload CSV files containing milk data enables users to obtain predictions for multiple samples simultaneously, enhancing efficiency in quality assessment processes. Furthermore, the detailed classification report and visualizations offered by the application contribute to a comprehensive understanding of the model's performance and the distribution of predicted quality grades. Overall, this project serves as a practical tool for dairy industry professionals seeking to ensure high standards of milk quality control and assurance.

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